

THE ROLE OF THE AMERICAN DREAM IN WOLT WILTMAN'S POEMS

Fayzullayeva Nigina Sur'at qizi

Asia International University

Department of History and Philology

fayzullayevaniginasuratqizi@oxu.uz

[https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.10034939](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10034939)

Abstract. Learning about the "American dream" and the "relationship between America and Walt Whitman" is undoubtedly challenging. You can find some key information about them in this article. There have been detractors of the American way of life throughout history. The emphasis on individualism and capitalism that Americans place leads to materialism, consumerism, and a lack of worker solidarity, according to some critics.

Key words: equality, social mobility, democracy, rights, and "Leaves of Grass".

РОЛЬ АМЕРИКАНСКОЙ МЕЧТЫ В СТИХАХ УОЛТА УИТМЕНА

Аннотация. Изучение "американской мечты" и "отношений между Америкой и Уолтом Уитменом", несомненно, является сложной задачей. Вы можете найти некоторую ключевую информацию о них в этой статье. На протяжении всей истории были недоброжелатели американского образа жизни. По мнению некоторых критиков, акцент, который американцы делают на индивидуализме и капитализме, ведет к материализму, потребительству и отсутствию солидарности трудящихся.

Ключевые слова: равенство, социальная мобильность, демократия, права и "Листья травы".

Wolt Wiltman, a renowned poet known for his introspective and thought-provoking works, often explores the concept of the American Dream in his poetry. The American Dream, a notion deeply ingrained in American society, represents the belief in upward mobility, opportunity, and success. In his poems, Wiltman examines both the allure and the challenges associated with this dream, delving into its impact on individuals and society. This article aims to explore the role of the American Dream in Wiltman's poetry, shedding light on its complexities and contradictions.

The Illusion of Attainability: Wiltman's poems often expose the illusory nature of the American Dream, challenging the notion that anyone can achieve success and prosperity through hard work alone. He poignantly highlights the systemic barriers and inequalities that hinder certain individuals' pursuit of this dream, such as racial discrimination, poverty, and limited opportunities. Wiltman prompts readers to question whether the American Dream truly exists for everyone or if it remains an unattainable ideal.

Materialism and Consumerism: Another aspect of the American Dream that Wiltman dissects in his poetry is the obsession with material wealth and consumerism. He critiques the notion that accumulation of possessions and wealth equates to personal fulfillment and happiness. Wiltman's poems often emphasize the emptiness and soullessness that can result from an unwavering pursuit of material success, urging readers to reassess their values and priorities.

Loss of Identity and Authenticity: Wiltman's exploration of the American Dream also delves into its potential impact on individual identity. He questions whether conformity and assimilation, often associated with the American Dream, lead to a loss of authenticity and self-

expression. Wiltman's poems examine the pressures to conform to societal norms and expectations, challenging readers to embrace their individuality and resist compromising their true selves for the sake of fitting into the mold of the American Dream.

Search for Meaning and Fulfillment: In his poetry, Wiltman presents a nuanced view of the American Dream by highlighting the inherent human desire for meaning and fulfillment. He portrays individuals who may have achieved material success but still feel a sense of emptiness and disillusionment. Through his exploration of the American Dream, Wiltman encourages readers to focus on personal growth, spirituality, and genuine human connections as paths to true happiness and fulfillment.

Hope and Resilience: While Wiltman's poems often critique the American Dream's flaws and limitations, they also offer glimpses of hope and resilience. Amidst the disillusionment and challenges, Wiltman's characters sometimes find the strength to redefine their own version of success and create their own paths towards fulfillment. This illustrates the possibility of transcending the narrow confines of the traditional American Dream and forging a unique, authentic journey.

Conclusion: Uolt Wiltman's poems provide a multi-dimensional exploration of the American Dream, examining its allure, contradictions, and limitations. Through his nuanced and thought-provoking verses, Wiltman prompts readers to question the ideals ingrained in American society and encourages them to seek personal growth, authenticity, and true fulfillment rather than being solely driven by material success. Wiltman's poetry invites us to reflect on the complexities of the American Dream and the importance of redefining our own notions of success and happiness.

REFERENCES

1. Fayzullayeva, N. S. qizi. (2023). Theoretical Views on the Use of the Term "Concept" in Cognitive Linguistics. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 3(5), 27–31. Retrieved from <https://www.inovatus.es/index.php/ejine/article/view/1685>
2. Fayzullayeva, N. (2023). USAGE OF THE FLORA IN THE EARLY MODERN ENGLISH POETRY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 36–39. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24078>
3. Sur'at qizi Fayzullayeva, N., & Kilicheva, M. R. (2022). UOLT UILTMAN NASRIDA "AMERIKA ORZUSI" KONSEPTI. *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON LEARNING AND TEACHING*, 1(8), 574-576.
4. OXUNJONOVICH, Q. Z. (2022). CHANGES OF LYULI IDENTITY. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 74-83.
5. Okhunjonovich, K. Z. (2023). THE EDUCATIONAL VALUE OF NATIONAL CUSTOMS AND TRADITIONS IN THE ERA OF GLOBALIZATION. *American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 18, 64-66.
6. Okhunjonovich, K. Z. (2021). Self-Awareness of Gypsies: Traditionality and Modernity. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 2(7), 33-42.
7. Корғдиев, З. О. (2016). ACTIVITIES OF AMUDARYA FLOTILLA AT THE END OF

- THE NINETEENTH CENTURY-BEGINNING OF THE TWENTIETH CENTURY HISTORY ("TURKESTAN COLLECTION" MATERIALS). *Ученый XXI века*, (12 (25)), 20-22.
8. Корёгдиев, З. О. (2016). GOLD EMBROIDERY OF BUKHARA. *Ученый XXI века*, (12).
 9. Zayniddinova, T. N. (2021). The Image of the Eastern Ruler in the Works of Christopher Marlowe. *Central Asian Journal Of Social Sciences And History*, 2(10), 10-14.
 10. Zayniddinova, T. N. (2022). The Problem of "A Strong Personality" in Shakespeare's Dramas: Richard III and Macbeth. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 20, 7-10.
 11. Zayniddinova, T. N. (2022). Lyrical Dialogue in Shakespeare's Poems as a Reflection of Renaissance Anthropocentrism and a Strong Personality. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 21, 120-125.
 12. Ташева, Н. З. (2022). КРИСТОФЕР МАРЛОУ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ): ТАМЕРЛЕН ВЕЛИКИЙ КАК ТИП ЛИЧНОСТИ ВОСТОЧНОГО ПРАВИТЕЛЯ. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(2), 234-239.
 13. Zayniddinova, T. N. (2022). THE CHARACTER OF STRONG PERSONALITY ACCORDINGLY WITH EASTERN THEMATICS IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S PLAY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 2(08), 9-14.
 14. Zayniddinova, T. N. (2022). STRONG PERSONALITY'S ARTISTIC AND POETIC REFLECTION IN THE RENAISSANCE EPOCH. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 2(11), 43-51.
 15. nafisa Zayniddinova, T. (2022). Lexico-Semantic Word Production as a Way of Forming Theater Terminology of the English Language. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(10), 144-150.
 16. Zayniddinova, T. N., & Sharofiddinovich, S. S. (2021). General cultural and educational values of ancient-classic latin language. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 2(5), 77-80.
 17. Zayniddinova, T. N. (2023). CHARACTERIZATION OF THE IMAGE OF AMIR TEMUR IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S DRAMA "TAMERLANE THE GREAT". *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(02), 36-43.
 18. Zayniddinova, T. N. (2023). CHARACTERIZATION OF THE IMAGE OF AMIR TEMUR IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S DRAMA "TAMERLANE THE GREAT". *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(02), 36-43.
 19. Tasheva, N. (2023). EXPRESSION OF LEXICAL-SEMANTIC AND SOCIO-SPIRITUAL PARAMETERS IN THE CREATION OF GREAT HUMAN FIGURES IN ENGLISH RENAISSANCE DRAMA. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(21), 50-57.
 20. Tasheva, N. (2023). LINGUISTIC AND STYLISTIC FEATURES OF THE TRAGEDY "TAMERLANE THE GREAT". *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 2(8), 11-14.
 21. Tasheva, N. (2023). "TAMERLANE THE GREAT" AS A PHENOMENON OF THE WORLDVIEW OF RENAISSANCE HUMANISM. *Педагогика и психология в*

- современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 2(9), 24-27.
22. Tasheva, N. (2023). EXPLORING THE RICH TAPESTRY OF LINGUISTICS: A COMPREHENSIVE OVERVIEW. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(11), 51-57.
 23. Tasheva, N. (2023). SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF LEXEMES WITHIN THE CONCEPT OF THE IDEA OF THE GREAT MAN IN MARLOWE'S DRAMA "TAMERLANE THE GREAT". *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 2(18), 90-93.
 24. Tasheva, N. (2023). EXPRESSION OF LEXICAL-SEMANTIC AND SOCIO-EDUCATIONAL PARAMETERS IN THE CREATION OF A GREAT HUMAN FIGURE IN ENGLISH RENAISSANCE DRAMA: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 2(7), 11-14.
 25. Tasheva, N. (2023). THE ROLE OF CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL ENGLISH DURING THE RENAISSANCE. *Models and methods in modern science*, 2(7), 14-19.
 26. Tasheva, N. (2023). THE IMAGE OF THE EAST IN THE PLAY "TAMERLANE THE GREAT" BY K. MARLOWE. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(3), 113-120.
 27. Tasheva, N. (2023). THE GREAT TAMBURLEN AS THE PSYCHOTYPE OF THE EASTERN RULER IN THE POETRY OF CHRISTOPHER MARLOW. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(4), 52-58.
 28. Tasheva, N. (2022). INDIVIDUALISM OF THE PHENOMENON OF A STRONG PERSONALITY IN THE AGE OF THE RENAISSANCE. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(13), 454-462.
 29. Orifjonovich, O. A. (2023). METAFORANING KO'P TARMOQLI VA FANLARARO O'RGANILISHI.
 30. Ollomurodov, A. (2023). MULTIDISCIPLINARY AND INTERDISCIPLINARY STUDY OF METAPHOR. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 136-139.
 31. Sulaymonovna, Q. N., & Orifjonovich, O. A. (2022). KONSEPTUAL METAFORALARNING LINGVOMADANIY HAMDA KOGNITIV XUSUSIYATLARI VA TIL TARAQQIYOTIDA TUTGAN ORNI. *Scientific Impulse*, 1 (3), 594-600.
 32. Sulaymonovna, Q. N., & Orifjonovich, O. A. (2022). KONSEPTUAL METAFORALARNING LINGVOMADANIY HAMDA KOGNITIV XUSUSIYATLARI VA TIL TARAQQIYOTIDA TUTGAN ORNI. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(3), 594-600.
 33. Xalilova, K. K. (2023). ACADEMIC VOCABULARY. HOW TO TEACH AND STUDY IT. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 78-80.
 34. Adizovna, S. M. (2023). DEVELOPING SUMMARY WRITING SKILL IN ACADEMIC WRITING.
 35. Berdiyeva, S. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF ROLE PLAYING ACTIVITIES IN IMPROVING LEARNERS' LANGUAGE SKILLS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(9), 75-78.

36. Jabborova Aziza Jobirovna. (2023). THE CATEGORY OF ASPECT IN ENGLISH GRAMMAR. Academia Science Repository, 4(05), 10–27. Retrieved from <http://academiascience.com/index.php/repo/article/view/443>
37. Bafoeva, R. (2023). INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK MAQOLLARINING KOGNITIV TAHLILI. World of Science, 6(6), 207-211
38. Sadullayev, U. . (2023). THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN NEIGHBORHOOD MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN. Modern Science and Research, 2(9), 132–135.
39. Tursunova, M. (2023). BADIY TARJIMA ASARLARDA ASLIYAT MUAMMOSI TADQIQI. Interpretation and researches, 1(8).
40. Tursunova, M. (2023). BADIY TARJIMADA LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK XUSUSIYATLAR. Журнал: Союз Науки и Образования, 5(2), 12-15.
41. Utkirovna, B. S. (2023). Characteristics of the Works of Charles Dickens. European Science Methodical Journal, 1(3), 24-28.
42. Utkerovna, B. S. (2023). SHUM BOLA ASARINING TARJIMASIDA TARJIMON MAHORATI. DENMARK" THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS IN MODERN SOCIETY", 14(1).
43. Ismatovna, I. L. Goals and Techniques for Teaching Grammar. International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education, 4(2), 33-34.
44. Nosirova, D. (2023). TYPOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PARTS OF SPEECH OF THE RUSSIAN, UZBEK, AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES AND THEIR TEACHING METHODS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION. Modern Science and Research, 2(4), 564–567. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/scienceresearch/article/view/19393>